

LOCAL ELECTRONIC STRUCTURE AT ALL SITES ON MICROFACET MODELS OF $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ - WHICH OXYGEN SITES ARE VACANT?

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The Local Electronic Density of States for up to 13 nonequivalent Ti and O surface atoms in the vicinity of a microfacet on reconstructed $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$, for five different models of a microfacet were computed. Our calculations indicate that the most likely vacant site is not the one previously identified on the basis of multiple-scattering calculations.

Our electronic structure algorithm scales linearly, $O(N)$, with a system size. Computational speed of 8.5 billion floating point operations per second for a non-periodic rutile systems of up to 1,105,920 atoms was achieved.

During the last four years a number of refined experimental studies of the rutile $TiO_2(100)$ surface have appeared in the literature [1-5]. With sophisticated experimental methods such as STM, glancing angle X-ray diffraction and LEED, the researchers were able to observe surface reconstruction and the appearance of $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ microfacets. The surface electronic valence-band structure of $TiO_2(100)$ and (110) faces was studied recently using angle-resolved photoemission [6]. It is hoped that by understanding the atomic and electronic structure of rutile surface, and especially the effects of surface steps and microfacets, the mechanism of photocatalytic decomposition of water observed by Fujisima and Honda in 1972 could be better understood [7,1]

While experiments give more new insights into the complex structure of surfaces, there has been rather slow progress in theoretical description of such systems. The electronic structure of rutile surfaces, both ideal and containing point defects was studied by Munnix and Schmeits [8-11].

The theoretical description of non-periodic structures poses formidable difficulties. When periodicity of infinite solid is lost one can no longer resort to simplifications offered by the Bloch Theorem and usually computations need to be done in direct space. Further, if large

scale corrugations on the surface are to be included, the methods applicable for clusters or simpler atomic steps could prove to be (still) limited. Yang *et al.*, [12] computed the electronic structure for a stepped *Cu(110)* surface using the recursive Green function method. Their sample was constructed from a supercell consisting of 150 atoms distributed over 5 layers and 25 chains. The electronic structure was computed for four atoms adjusting to the square angle atomic step.

An interesting computationally feasible alternative, based on the recursion method and the augmented-space formalism was recently proposed by Saha *et al.* [13]. It still needs to be proven if it can be applied to realistic systems since, as authors note: "In spite of its immense potential the method could not be used for practical calculations because of the large dimension of the augmented space" [13]. It was exciting to see that *ab initio* method of Car-Parrinello was successfully applied to study dissociation of water at a stepped *MgO* surface [14]. These computations showed that in contrast to the perfect surface, dissociation of water proceeds very rapidly at the stepped surface.

In the present work we use the equation of motion method (EoM) [15,16] to compute the local electronic densities of states for up to thirteen outermost nonequivalent *Ti* and *O* atoms in the vicinity of a microfacet. Five different microfacet models of reconstructed *TiO₂(100)* 1×3 surface which we studied will be described below. The equation of motion method was described in detail in a number of previous publications; *e.g.* see [17,18] for further references.

The crystallographic structure of ideal rutile *TiO₂* [19,20] and its most stable surfaces (110) and (100) [21] is well known. The tetragonal unit cell consists of two *Ti* and four *O* atoms. The titanium atoms occupy the positions (0, 0, 0) and $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ whereas oxygens are at the positions $\pm(x, x, 0)$, and $\pm(\frac{1}{2} + x, \frac{1}{2} - x, \frac{1}{2})$, where $x = 0.306 \pm 0.001$ [19].

Based on data derived from LEED symmetry and photoemission spectra Muryn *et al.* (1991) proposed the missing row model (MR) for the reconstructed *TiO₂(100)* surface. Soon after, Zschack *et al.* [3] found that the microfacet model (MM) (Figure 1) was in better agreement with glancing angle X-ray diffraction and LEED measurements than the missing row model. We used all five models: missing row (MR), microfacet model (MM) and microfacet models A, B and C (MMA, MMB and MMC respectively) to study the effect of the local environment on the local electronic density of states (LDOS).

This type of information is especially useful when analysing Scanning Tunneling Microscopy images. There is clearly a need to compute the electronic properties in mesoscopic or even nano-structures at quantum mechanics level taking into account exact composition of a system, including both point and extended defects. Recent-

ly single impurity atoms were studied in heterostructure-defined mesoscopic structures [22]. STM images of reconstructed and reduced surfaces of $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ were obtained by a number of groups [2,5]. In all studies the images are obtained at positive sample bias, *i.e.* the electrons tunnel from the tip into unoccupied Ti $3d$ states. It was reported that the images at negative tip bias could not be obtained. This means that the STM probe the positions of the Ti atoms and can not distinguish between different reduced surface models (MMA, MMB or MM-C). The results of our calculations attempt to answer the question: which model is physically realised?

The massively parallel implementation of the equation-of-motion program designed for array processor SIMD architecture [17,18] was modified specifically for MIMD (as well as SIMD) machines. The sample can now be rotated, arbitrary crystallographic faces can be exposed and the extended surface defects such as steps, islands and microfacets can easily be built as software masks. The local electronic density of states for up to thirteen nonequivalent atoms on the surface of microfacet for five models of microfacet (MR, MM, MMA, MMB and MMC) were computed using the new version of our program. The full results will be published elsewhere. Here we present the characteristic results for the Microfacet Model at positions indicated in Figure 2.

The typical results are presented in Figure 3. The LDOS for all four models derived from Microfacet Model are very similar. One striking feature is complete lack of covalent mixing and narrow s and p bands at oxygen site $O5.2$. This feature is present in all three models (MM, MMA and MMB). We interpret this as a lack of bonding of $O5.2$ atom at a microfacet. It would mean that Microfacet Model C is the most likely to represent the reduced reconstructed $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ surface. This result is different from the conclusions of Hardman *et al.*, [5]. Based on time-reversed dynamical LEED formalism those authors suggest that Microfacet Model A is the one which gives the closest agreement with their LEED experimental data.

The production code was run on the CRAY C9016E/16256-4 vector-parallel machine with 16 processors, 256 Mwords memory and having 4.167 nanosecond clock. Depending on the size of the sample the program ran between 550 to 630 MFlops/s on a single processor C90. This means we achieved about 55% to 63% efficiency of a single vector processor of CRAY C90. The sample sizes are presented in the following table.

Each unit cell contains six atoms. The dimensions of the largest sample were $18 \times 22 \times 28nm$. The results of benchmarks are presented in Figure 4.

The running time was defined as the total CPU time divided by the number of processors which ran a particular job. The running time defined this way differs slightly (up to about 15%) from the wallclock figures given on

completion of each job. The discrepancy is attributed to the fact that we run our program on a busy machine with many jobs competing for the resources. For a given sample size the slope of each curve decreases with the number of processors. This indicates deterioration of performance of each processor as the number of processors used grows. The best performance achieved was 8.5 GFlops when we run our code on 16 processors (wallclock 452s, system size 552960 atoms).

Figure 5 shows that the computational complexity of the vector-parallel version of the equation of motion program is linear with the size of the sample.

There is a need for very fast and efficient codes to calculate the electronic structure of novel complex materials. The search for electronic structure algorithms which scale linearly is an intense field of research [23–25]. Defects engineering might lead to exciting new materials and devices. The equation-of-motion method, as implemented in this work, can be used to study disordered transition metal oxides, amorphous semiconductors, the electronic structure of random point and extended defects and their influence on the electronic properties of materials. The current version of the program, developed specifically for MIMD or massively parallel architectures scales identically in all three spatial dimensions of a sample. It is possible to manipulate a sample, rotate it, study various crystallographic faces and extended surface defects.

With the program reported in this work we studied the local electronic structure of *Ti* and *O* atoms in the vicinity of $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ microfacets. The samples were up to 1,105,920 atoms or $18 \times 22 \times 28nm$ in size. The wallclock time for the sample of 24576 atoms for all thirteen atoms (each atom requires new initialization) took about 730 seconds (2864s CPU) on four processors of sixteen processor CRAY C90. The peak speed achieved in benchmarks was 8.5 GFlops/s.

The CRAY part of this project was developed on the CSIRO Supercomputing Facility CRAY Y-MP4/464 in Melbourne. The computations were done on CRAY C916/16256 and CRAY C916/12512 located at Cray Headquarters in Egan, MN. These machines are part of Cray Computer Network. Some preliminary results presented in this paper were communicated in the Proceedings *High Performance Computing 1995*. The fragments which are duplicated are reprinted by permission from *High Performance Computing 1995*, pp.101-106, 1995 Simulation Councils, Inc.

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FIG. 1. Microfacet Model of the $TiO_2(100)1 \times 3$ reconstruction (after Ref. [5]). Oxygen is represented by large and titanium by small circles. The oxygen vacancy sites studied in this work are labelled by letters A, B and C.

FIG. 2. Five *Ti* (small black circles) and eight *O* (large black circles) atom sites at which the LDOS was computed.

FIG. 3. The Local Electronic Density of States for surface atoms in Microfacet Model (MM) at positions indicated in Figure 2. Note complete lack of covalent mixing and spread of bands at site *O*5.2.

FIG. 4. Computation time as the function of the system size for different numbers of Cray C90 processors employed. The linear scaling is seen for all hardware configurations.

FIG. 5. The linear coefficient which illustrate the speed-up achieved using progressively more Cray C90 processors. Black triangles is the data from Figure 4, open circles are for $1/n$ ideal speed-up (n is the number of processors).

TABLE I. *TiO₂* model system sizes

System size $a \times a \times c$	Number of atoms
$6 \times 6 \times 6$	1296
$10 \times 10 \times 12$	7200
$12 \times 12 \times 12$	10368
$16 \times 16 \times 16$	24574
$18 \times 18 \times 18$	34992
$20 \times 20 \times 20$	48000
$24 \times 24 \times 24$	82944
$81 \times 81 \times 10$	393660
$45 \times 45 \times 42$	510300
$40 \times 48 \times 48$	552960
$40 \times 48 \times 96$	1105920

Microfacet Model

